

**THE APPOINTMENT OF CLARITA CARLOS
AS PHILIPPINE PRESIDENT'S
NATIONAL SECURITY ADVISER:
A SENTIMENT ANALYSIS**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 14
Pages: 1240-1250
Document ID: 2023PEMJ1332
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10096423
Manuscript Accepted: 2023-8-11

The Appointment of Clarita Carlos as Philippine President's National Security Adviser: A Sentiment Analysis

Gideon S. Sumayo*, Danilo G. Baradillo

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study delved into the sentiments expressed by the public Facebook users regarding the appointment of Clarita Carlos as the Philippine president's national security adviser. Utilizing a qualitative approach with text mining, the research focused on a dataset comprising 100 selected Facebook comments from users in response to an online news article posted by GMA News. To identify commonly used words and assess user sentiments, the study harnessed the capabilities of Orange software. The study revealed that the most frequently used words as generated by Word Cloud in Orange software are carlo, prof, clarita, security, professor, congratulation, god, good, national, and bless. Employing thematic analysis, the research unveiled the prevalent sentiments in the Facebook user comments, which revolved around four emerging themes: (1) eloquence and female leadership in politics, (2) gender and leadership in the Philippine government, (3) corruption concerns in professor Carlos's potential appointment, and (4) security concerns regarding professor Carlos's appointment. Furthermore, the analysis demonstrated that the sentiments encompassed both positive and negative polarities, with some users adopting a neutral stance. The study underscores the value of employing sentiment analysis as a means to gain fresh insights into pressing issues, particularly within the context of ongoing national concerns. For educators, insights may be used to inform students about women in leadership and public perceptions, enriching discussions on gender dynamics and leadership with real-world sentiment analysis examples.

Keywords: *Clarita Carlos, facebook, national security adviser, sentiment analysis, Philippines*

Introduction

In today's generation, social media such as Facebook plays an integral part in the lives of billions of people. Interviews and news, whether pose positive or negative outcomes, are being shown through posts, pages, or walls, and Facebook has been the medium for it (Pudaruth, Moheeputh, Permessur, & Chamroo, 2018; Syahriani, Yana, & Santoso, 2020). It cannot be denied that Facebook is now utilized to share sentiments to any subjective information. One can even voice out what they have in mind, whether it is positive or negative. Hence, this study would like to embark on one of the controversial issues in the Philippines, the appointment of Professor Clarita Carlos as the national security adviser to the president, which gathered different attitudes toward it.

Being the national security adviser to the president is considered to be a high-ranking position; its similarity to the position in the Armed Forces of the Philippines and other security organizations ascertain to a great extent and intensified role, which a woman from the lenses of a male-dominated office will think negatively (Goldman, 1973; Gustavsen, 2013). That is why women's representation through Prof. Clarita Carlos's appointment is one way of putting an end to the dearth of women representation in the workforce less invaded

by a woman persona.

Just recently, the pronouncement of President Elect Ferdinand Marcos elated so many Filipinos; however, it is not true for all. Many were not in agreement with the decision of the president. Thus, divided the people from different points of perspective. With this, the researcher is inspired to explore the problematic issue through sentiment analysis.

To continue, there were numerous researches conducted as regards sentiment analysis, but most are on online crimes (Surroop, Canoo, & Pudaruth, 2016), political campaign posts (Almazan & Cruz, 2020), and presidential candidates (Syahriani, Yana, & Santoso, 2020). In my locality, considering the issue is Philippine-based, I have not come across research that delves into this matter; thus, it imbued me to study and unveil the sentiments of the public Facebook users.

In this research undertaking, the researchers aim to contribute to Psychology and Education by unveiling the sentiment of the Filipino people giving us fresh insights as to the openness to the idea of allowing a woman to lead in a patriarchal imbued country when it comes to leading the defense and security. It is crucial to emphasize that the findings of this paper will not only enhance our understanding but will also play a pivotal role in informing decision-making processes. By listening to the prevailing public sentiment, this research will aid in ensuring the principles of

democracy are upheld and respected.

Moreover, the study being undertaken is significant to the President of the Philippines as this may provide him insights if his decision is amenable to his countrymen, whether the expressed sentiments are positive, negative, or neutral. More so, the salient findings may provide a cornerstone to other researchers who would like to understand the opinions of the people through a new methodology, sentiment analysis.

Research Questions

This study will deal with exploring the sentiments of the public as regards the appointment of Prof. Clarita Carlos as the National Security Adviser of the Philippine President. More specifically, this qualitative study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the frequently used words that define the opinion of the public on the appointment of Clarita Carlos as the Philippine President's National Security Adviser?
2. How is the heatmap describing the sentiments of the public on the appointment of Clarita Carlos as the Philippine President's National Security Adviser?
3. What sentiment analysis best describes the opinion of the public on the appointment of Clarita Carlos as the Philippine President's National Security Adviser?

Literature Review

Women in Philippine National Security Council

The National Security Council's role is to advise the President on the integration of domestic, foreign, and military policies related to national security. It is also said to be the President's primary arm for coordinating these policies among various government departments and agencies in national security matters (Executive Order No. 292, s. 1987 - The Administrative Code of 1987). However, news alarmed so many Filipinos when President-Elect Ferdinand Marcos appointed Clarita Carlos, a retired political science professor, as his National Security Adviser, who will be one of his cabinet members (Patinio, 2022).

Report presented that the appointment of Dr. Clarita Carlos as National Security Adviser (NSA) is a welcome development. Dr. Carlos is the first woman NSA. She is more than qualified for the job of NSA (Patinio, 2022). On the one hand, Lorenzana, in the Punongbayan's (2022) report, articulated that the incoming national security adviser Clarita Carlos will

look closely at the National Task Force to End Local Communist Armed Conflict, and solve New People's Army problem through a whole-of-nation approach instead of resorting to military solutions and ways. He added that the adviser would not have a hard time fitting into her job and understanding what the DND is doing since she has been connected to the National Defense College, where she served as the former president and her field of specialization is on national defense and foreign policy.

Her appointment in this male-dominated high-ranking position paved the way for giving gender equality in the workplace. It ends the stereotype of females have no background when it comes to national defense and military parlance. According to Buan (2022), in recent administrations, the NSA position has typically gone to former military officers or politicians with a defense background or military experience on the ground, which is in contrast to Professor Carlos' qualifications.

Women and Leadership

In the Philippine context, women's representation in terms of holding leadership positions is not unusual. Filipinos, for example, have already installed two female presidents and two female vice presidents since the end of the Marcos dictatorship (David, Albert, Vizmanos, 2017). Additionally, according to new LinkedIn data published in the World Economic Forum's 2022 Global Gender Gap Report, more women have been hired in leadership roles since 2015, with the Philippines seeing the largest increase among all Asia Pacific (APAC) markets studied.

In addition, women as well have entered the armed forces. The armed forces are primarily male-dominated industry. It depicts one of society's "most gendered realms." However, changes in occupational and bureaucratic structures resulted from women joining the military, which constitutes having leadership positions. Yet still, women in the military were restricted to administrative positions, and high-ranking positions were not that easy given. The impact of transformations in security sector governance and significant policy initiatives provided for comprehensive changes in the Philippines, resulting in a massive increase in the quantity and quality of women's military involvement but few with leadership roles and functions (Cuaresma, Lopez, Reyes, & Avellanoza, 2020).

Women are frequently viewed as conflict victims. However, this perspective obscures the critical roles that women play as leaders, particularly in helping to end the conflict, developing post-conflict reintegration efforts and economic life, and even leading the

organization of camps for internally displaced people (Norville, 2011).

More so, even in other fields of leadership such as CEOs, senior executives, and boards (i.e., chairpersons, independent directors, and all directors) of the Philippine publicly traded firms are still in favor of males, yet proportions of women in CEOs, senior executives, chairs, and other board members have been gradually increasing since 2003. However, with the Philippines' aim to address the gender gap, it was able to be touted as one of the world's top performers in closing the gap among firm management positions.

In the international context, particularly in the setting of the pandemic, the prowess of women when the chips are down is deliberately demonstrated. According to Orme (2021), female political leaders have coped with the pandemic fatigue and problems differently and often better than men. He continued by stating that women are perceived to have done a better job than men. They scored higher in crisis-related competencies such as taking the initiative, acting with resilience, practicing self-development, and displaying integrity. As in politics, symbolic landmarks have been reached.

Corruption in Leadership

According to Kreuzer (2009), the Philippines are a gambling republic in which politicians hold power without virtue, dominating through capital, coercion, and crime. He went on to say that individual power holders are bosses who use "guns, goons, and gold" to gain, maintain, or enhance their positions of power.

Sentiment Analysis

Since the last decade, sentiment analysis has been an active area of study among many computational linguists. However, with the unprecedented increase in the amount of unstructured text generated online, the field of sentiment analysis is gaining popularity and becoming increasingly important for decision-making in large businesses, governmental organizations, and many other organizations (Surroop, Canoo, & Pudaruth, 2016).

Nowadays, the internet is constantly flooded with various applications and digital media through which people from various backgrounds and expertise share their thoughts and opinions on a wide range of topics and events, such as national security. Typically, people share information in textual form and are available to the eyes of the public (Razali et al., 2021). In the study of Surroop, Canoo, and Pudaruth (2016), they explicated that sentiment analysis could be a good

source of determining whether the opinions are positive, negative, or very negative. Hence, this research has dealt with the polarities of the sentiments and provided different keywords to illustrate essential themes that defined the opinion of the research topic understudied.

More importantly, the sentiment analysis also tries to uncover the user's decision and point of view in an easy and accurate way. The identification and generation of the data can be pulled through software in text-mining such as Orange, which will lessen the time of extraction from the corpus, and will be contrary if extraction is done manually. The automatic function in this regard allows the researcher ample time to divulge the needed remarks for a certain inquiry, such as problems in text mining, movie user reviews, social tweets, social media-based opinion mining, political campaigns, political discourse, entertainment (Almazan & Cruz, 2020; Melendres & Barea, 2020; Rahmath, 2014; Smeureanu & Bucur, 2012; Umar & Chiroma, 2016).

Methodology

The study utilized the qualitative method employing sentiment analysis. This research design will help understand the unique sentiments of the public as regards the appointment of an influential woman as the national security adviser of the Philippine president. The sentiment analysis tries to uncover the user's decision and point of view in an easy and accurate way. The identification and generation of the data can be pulled through software in text-mining such as Orange, which will lessen the time of extraction from the corpus, and will be contrary if extraction is done manually. The automatic function in this regard allows the researcher ample time to divulge the needed remarks for a certain inquiry, such as problems in text mining, movie user reviews, social tweets, social media-based opinion mining, political campaigns, political discourse, entertainment (Almazan & Cruz, 2020; Melendres & Barea, 2020; Rahmath, 2014; Smeureanu & Bucur, 2012; Umar & Chiroma, 2016).

In this study, sentiment analysis was used to determine whether public opinions are positive, neutral, or negative. The approach that was employed here is polarity-based, which means the pieces of texts are classified as either positive or negative.

Data Source

The corpora of this research were the sentiments posted by the public in the comment section of the GMA News' post. These were the comments found on

the episode by The Mangahas Interviews entitled “BBM Cabinet: Dr. Clarita Carlos, Incoming National Security Adviser” which was posted by the GMA News Official Facebook page. There were 100 comments selected for analysis.

Procedure

According to Creswell (2007), to gather the needed data properly, the data collection must adhere to four basic processes: interviews, observation, audio-related materials, and documents connected to the research. For the part of this research, I will employ a collection of comments from the post of GMA News.

The data collection started by visiting the GMA News post on Facebook and choosing the 100 comments randomly. After identifying the comments, these are all transferred in the Microsoft Excel file. Some of the comments were written in Filipino; thus, they were translated first to English for clarity. After the careful selection and translation of the comments, they were subjected to the Orange text mining application for refinement. The comments come with lots of unwanted marks, such as punctuation marks, emoticons, and URLs, which are not desired for sentiment analysis; thus, filtration through pre-processing the texts was done to get meaningful data.

The purpose of pre-processing data is to perform data cleansing and transformation on previously collected data Canrakerta et al. (2018). During this phase, several steps are taken to collect the final data used for word weighting and sentiment analysis to assess community satisfaction with the decision of the President of the Philippines to appoint Clarita Carlos as National Security Adviser.

The output of pre-processing data is a collection of terms that researchers use to search for terms as scoring season analysis material.

Data Sources

The information gathered during the identification and selection of the comments will be combined and find the common themes that emerge in the study. The transcribed and translated data from the comments were scrutinized using Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis. Specifically, the following procedure of thematic analysis was performed, such as becoming familiar with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining themes, and writing up.

For sentiment analysis, the texts underwent pre-processing using the Orange text mining software, and the sentiments were already classified into positive, negative, and neutral using the sentiment score.

Ethical Considerations

To safeguard the anonymity and privacy of the Facebook users, the researchers employed codes to reference their comments, thereby ensuring the preservation of ethical considerations.

Results

Frequently Used Words in the Opinions of the Public on Prof. Carlos Clarita's Appointment as National Security Adviser

Table 1 presents the generated frequently used words in the corpora. These are the words that are common in the comments gathered from a post on GMA News. The identification of the top ten frequently used words was determined through the Word Cloud feature of Orange text mining software.

Table 1. *Frequently Used Words in the Opinions of the Public on Prof. Carlos Clarita's Appointment as National Security Adviser*

Rank	Frequency	Words
1	53	carlo
2	35	prof
3	25	clarita
4	23	security
5	22	professor
6	18	congratulation
7	17	god
8	15	good
9	14	national
10	13	bles

The most frequently used word is “Carlos,” which is employed in the comments 53 times, followed by “prof”, which is utilized 35 times. Another most frequently used word is “Clarita”. This word occurred 25 times. Next to it was the word “security,” which was used 23 times in the corpora. The word “professor” followed for it has an occurrence of 22. This word was followed by the word “congratulations”, which has 18 number of occurrences. The next word was “God”, which occurred 17 times in the corpora, followed by the word “good,” which had 15 numbers of occurrences, then

She's very smart. She deserves to be the adviser of PBBM. D – 55

Prof. Carlos deserves to be in Foreign affairs, but PBBM has the wide latitude to see and consider several factors, and perhaps that is the reason why he wishes Prof. Carlos to be the security adviser. (The security issues are both national and international). D – 69

Professor Clarita Carlos is a very intelligent woman and deserves to be the National Security Adviser of BBM. Congratulations. D – 39

Very smart, Professor Carlos. God bless and guide you always. The country needs someone like you to lead so it will prosper. D – 89

Imagine being publicly denied by her alumni because she was objective in her views and now become the nation's best mind for international security by the president. Oh, I love this plot twist. D – 77

Corruption Concerns in Professor Carlos's Potential Appointment

In a high-ranking position, some Facebook users have seen this problem be engulfed by the newly appointed national security adviser. The public voiced out that she might only succumb to the lasting culture of corruption in the Philippines, and she will be corrupted by her power. It can be inferred that her appointment has garnered the same sentiments, just like those who were given different appointments.

Corruption is a culture in the Philippines. For many years, corruption has been a problematic issue in the country. Some people in the comments claimed that corruption is seemingly a hopeless case and often happens when there is human intervention. The following comments below are extracted from the corpora to demonstrate this core idea:

Though I am optimistic about a solution to every problem, corruptions in the Philippines seem hopeless. Seem I inclined to believe that such bids are in our blood as Filipinos. D – 43

Correct. Corruption is a human condition that has become a culture in the government. D – 62

Correct, to reduce corruption is to reduce human intervention. D – 38

Corruption of Power. One of the reasons why people are afraid to trust again to those who were given appointments since the power that might be vested in these people might be used in devilish acts and might

propagate negative aftermath. This kind of perception stems from the standpoint that her appointment might be used by the leftist groups to strengthen their power and perhaps use her power for personal interest and gain. The following comment below is extracted from the corpora to demonstrate this core idea:

What makes her appointment problematic is that the leftist group may become powerful again. D – 88

Security Concerns Regarding Professor Carlos's Appointment

In this aspect, people have aired their insights that the appointed person is not capable of doing the job and would only bring harm to the security of the Philippines. It can be gleaned that what they are trying to point out was Professor Carlos does not have enough military training to address the perennial problems as regards security.

Lack of military training. The public is hesitant to give their full blessing to the appointed individual of the president. They think that the research engagement and academic standing are not enough basis to address problems in security concerns of the country. And what put her at a disadvantage position as she has no experience in the military ground. These perceptions can be best gleaned from the comments below:

I just hope military people in her job will also back Prof. Carlos up as a national security adviser. It is truly different from having a military experience when it comes to the national security aspect. The training and experience are different since those in the military have actual immersion on the ground, and they know the dynamics in the war, unlike Prof. Carlos, who is more on research and academics. She has no actual experience on the ground. She does not know how rebels and terrorist thinks. D – 97

Prof., you must consider retiring. Your knowledge is fitted in the classroom where theories can be fantasized to be working in the real world. Ric Manrique, who died a long time ago, you just knew today that he was a singer. Hahaha. D – 28

Table 2. Descriptions of the Sentiments of the Public on Prof. Carlos' Appointment

Essential Theme	Codes	Core Ideas
Eloquence and Female Leadership in Politics	Prof. Carlos is woman of substance.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Giving credible answers to the questions Manifesting fair reasoning Giving hooking insights She can lead.
Gender and Leadership in the Philippine Government	Prof. Carlos is the best leader for the position.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> She is the most qualified. She can give clear directions to the office.
Corruption Concerns in Professor Carlos's Potential Appointment	Corruption is a culture in the Philippines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Corruption is seemingly a hopeless case in the country Corruption happens where there is a human intervention
	Corruption of power	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leftist can strengthen their groups Use her power for personal gain
Security Concerns Regarding Professor Carlos's Appointment	Lack of military training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> She only has research and academics No experience in the military ground

In Table 3 below, the results revealed that the standpoint of the public on Prof. Clarita Carlos' Appointment as the National Security Adviser to the Philippine president was divided into three major categories. As shown in the table, 76% of the respondents shared a positive polarity, while 11% of them were negative polarity, and 13% are in neutral polarity.

Sample comments for positive polarity to demonstrate it clearly are the following:

Wow! Good exchange and sharing of knowledge between Malou and Professor Carlos. I love their conversations. D – 1

Congratulations, Prof. Carlos! You deserved much. God bless po. D – 4

Wow! Great! There is a standpoint. D – 8

The answers of Prof. Carlos are so honest. We will pray for you. May God bless! D – 16

Professor Clarita Carlos is a very intelligent woman and deserves to be the National Security Adviser of BBM. Congratulations. D – 39

Congratulations! Prof. Clarita Carlos. We have been waiting for this! D – 99

Sample comments for negative polarity to illustrate them clearly are the following:

The statement of Prof. Clarita Carlos contradicts what Pres. Elect PBBM stated in his recent interview with Boy Abunda that he would only let the ICC enter the Philippines as a tourist but not investigate nor intervene in our government. D – 15

It was good, but there is a saying that you tend to be

forgetful when you are getting old. I hope we know this situation since the whole Philippines will suffer from it. D – 17

Very nice interview and way better than the Presidential Interviews of Jessica Sojo. Interesting answers from Prof. Carlos. I was disappointed by the commercials. It disrupted the discussion so badly. Very annoying. D – 21

I dislike her now. 360 degrees from her being a panelist in the debate. D – 27

The host did not research well. In fairness, he answered the "Machiavelli" question adequately per the professor. Your question showed your political leanings. Cannot hide it. D - 34

Here are the comments which are under the neutral polarity:

She is the new Meriam Defensor Santiago! D – 9

Those who recruit the youth for the communist must be captured. D – 22

The right choice, Prof. Clarita. D – 25

Correct, to reduce corruption is to reduce human intervention. D – 38

Salute to you Professor Clarita Carlos. D – 54

Table 3. Sentiment Analysis of the Public on Prof. Clarita Carlos' Appointment

Polarity	Percentage
Positive	76%
Negative	11%
Neutral	13%

Figure 2. The doughnut representation of polarity

Discussion

Frequently Used Words in the Opinions of the Public on Prof. Carlos Clarita's Appointment as National Security Adviser

The findings revealed the most frequently used words in the comments of the public regarding the appointment of Professor Clarita Carlos as the National Security Adviser are following words are carlo, prof, clarita, security, professor, congratulation, god, good, national, and bless. These words have clearly defined how they view the appointment of Clarita Carlos as positive, negative, or neutral. The occurrences of these words, such as prof, professor, carlo, and clarita imply that addressing forms are seen as pivotal when articulating a sentiment. It can be understood that the people have high regard and respect for the person, and they see Prof. Carlos as someone who is worthy of being addressed using such honorifics, which are present in D-4, D-13, D-39, and D-72.

Security, congratulations, god, good, national, and bless are also utilized to express a certain attitude or a proposition towards the other interlocutor in his/her utterances. Like the word security, in the sentiment D-36, it was mentioned that a woman would have difficulty being the national security adviser. This could imply that the user here is being assertive as an illocutionary point. In the D-40, the word "Congratulations", on the one hand, when used by a Facebook user to give his sentiment that the user really admires the stand of the professor and the way she shares her knowledge about what is right is seen to be an expressive illocutionary point.

The sentiments with the word god and bless are both commissive illocutionary points. In their sentiment D-42, the word god was used to associate it with pleading with the Lord that He will bless the country as Prof. Clarita Carlos takes charge of the position. While the word 'bless' also has the same function, when integrated into the sentiment, it says that God will give the professor His blessings and grant her guidance as she leads the national security council.

Moreover, the word 'good' when associated with its sentiment D-87 was an assertive illocutionary point. The public user emphasized that the professor had good points and was able to leave a good impression on him. This could possibly happen when an individual has an experience with the person. It may provide the individual an actual grasp of the attitude

and behavior of the person since he/she is interacting or mingling with him/her.

Additionally, the word national is seen to be a directive illocutionary point since, based on the sentiment D-82, the public user wanted that the professor will help them as regards the international security concerns. The public user wants the professor to do something. It implies that the user is requesting in his sentiment.

Descriptions of the Sentiments of the Public on Prof. Carlos' Appointment

The emergent themes which described the sentiments shared by the public on Prof Carlos' Appointment were as follows: (1) Eloquence and Female Leadership in Politics, (2) Gender and Leadership in the Philippine Government, (3) Corruption Concerns in Professor Carlos's Potential Appointment, and (4) Security Concerns Regarding Professor Carlos's Appointment.

Eloquence and Female Leadership in Politics

Eloquence is how a political leader can be good with words and expressing things in a pleasing or persuasive manner. Eloquence can be seen in how good your points are and how you tailor your ideas which will make you someone who has substance when speaking or writing. In this study, it was revealed that the professor was a woman of substance based on the sentiments provided in D-40, D-63, D-47, D-81, D-49, and D-24. It can be assumed that she possesses the qualities the public would like to have for someone who will take over a high-ranking position. It implies as well that her eloquence is an advantage to the international security concerns and other aspects that relate to it the fact that she is well-versed and knowledgeable of the task at hand.

This sentiment basically conforms to what Orme (2021) claimed that female political leaders are competitive enough to have done a better job than men, especially in this time of the pandemic. It also enlightened us that women are no longer perceived to be adamant in terms of leading a high-ranking position. Norville (2021) iterated that women play as leaders particularly have the quality in leading organizations of camps.

Gender and Leadership in the Philippine Government

Leadership is the ability of an individual to lead and

influence a certain office or organization along with its subordinates or followers. Being a woman upfront in the Philippine government, holding a position is no longer an issue. But despite the efforts to address gender gaps in the country, there are still individuals who are not amenable to positioning a woman to lead a male-dominated position. Based on the sentiments in D-55 iterating that she deserves to be the adviser of PBBM, sentiment D-69 exuding that her expertise is one reason why she was chosen by the president, sentiments D-39 and D-89 accentuated that she is an intellect who deserves to lead the council, it can be assumed that multiple users are in favor of her budding administration as the national security adviser, despite being a woman.

The findings of the study corroborate the research of David, Albert, and Vizmanos (2017) that tells that the Philippines had two female presidents and two vice-presidents, which pertains to the leadership is also seen transcending from men to women. However, Cuaresma, Lopez Reyes, and Avellanoza (2020) stated that in the Armed Forces of the Philippines, still some administrative positions are limited to male officers, which perhaps is the reason why some could not give the nod on the appointment of the Clarita Carlos, and not welcome of her assumption to the office.

Corruption Concerns in Professor Carlos's Potential Appointment

Corruption is one of the many ill-sickening dilemmas in the Philippine government. And based on the sentiments shared by the public, they all have one thing in common—they emphasized that corruption is still prevalent in the country, and this situation might be experienced by the professor. According to Radics (2001), the Philippines has experienced total systematic affliction where practically all government offices and projects are prone to corruption. It implies that this culture of corruption might also overwhelm Professor Carlos, and her office might be overwhelmed by it knowing that government offices in the Philippines are seen to be likely to engage.

Another thing that the one user aired out was the corruption of power in the sentiment D-88. She might use her power so leftists can strengthen their groups. It implies that the user is reluctant to believe that the professor will not be corrupted by her power, provided that it has been a long problem in society, especially in the Philippines. This finding is consistent with Kreuzer's (2009) observation that the Philippines are a gambling republic in which politicians hold power without virtue, dominating through capital, coercion,

and crime. He went on to say that individual power holders are bosses who use "guns, goons, and gold" to gain, maintain, or enhance their positions of power. Hence, sentiment like one of the Facebook users aired out is acceptable since this power tripping has been the practice of many political leaders, and Prof. Clarita Carlos cannot be told that she will not do that and can only be proven as after an amount of time and service.

Security Concerns Regarding Professor Carlos's Appointment

The security aspect is one of the essential themes derived from the sentiments of the public, they think that security is at stake since the one who will take over has no experience in the military ground. They seem to think that her academic standing and research engagements are not enough basis for her to be considered as one of the options. It also implies that she cannot address the prevalent problems of the country as regards international and national security. Yet, these sentiments were not in congruence with the claims of Patonio (2022), in which he made mentioned that the professor is more than qualified for the position. Punongbayan (2022) even iterated that the professor will not have a hard time adjusting since she has been connected to the National Defense College, where she served as the former president, and her field of specialization is on national defense and foreign policy.

Moreover, these sentiments made describe security as normal since people are part of the security sector. According to Geneva Centre for Security Sector Governance (2015), the security sector is composed of personnel, institutions, and structures responsible for security provisions, management, and oversight at the national and local levels. Hence, if I may assume, the public has something to deal with it. They could give their remarks since they will be part of the system in which a person will take charge, and based on their comments, what they are only saying is that security will be at stake if it is given to someone who has no capacity or inkling of experience towards it. So, it is an impending case that the appointment of Professor Carlos could really pave the way for positive or negative sentiments, knowing that she will be the one responsible for international and national security concerns.

Sentiment Analysis of the Public on Prof. Clarita Carlos' Appointment

In the findings, it was revealed that three major categories were derived and these are positive polarity,

negative polarity, and neutral polarity. The appointment of Professor Clarita Carlos allows the public to share their sentiments on a social media platform. They are free to engage in discourse and could share their attitudes towards the issue being tackled. According to Pang and Lee (2008) and Razali et al. (2021), with the tremendous growth of online discussion groups and review sites, many researchers have engulfed themselves in the sentiment classification, which will predict an overall sentiment whether they are positive, negative, or neutral.

For positive polarity, the attitude of the public was full of felicitations. They were excited about the appointment of Professor Carlos. A word such as congratulations indeed expressed the feeling of positivity in her budding administration. According to Martin and White (2005), this kind of attitude is under the emotional region since the sentiment expressions express feelings, which are all derived from their comments. Hence, if they like the person, the idea, concept, or any other explicit information, then a positive polarity may be higher and could be found frequently in the sentiments.

As regards negative polarity, most of the comments are under the ethical region in which judgmental sentences involve the public or the appraiser evaluating an intelligent object. Based on the sentiments they have shared, they are criticizing the age, her contradictory sentiments to the pronouncements of the president, and being disliked since the SMNI debates. It was even revealed that negative polarity is not only limited to the comments of the public as regards the appointment rather, there was also positioning of other adverse comments, such as disappointment with the commercials and the political leanings of the interviewer. According to Cook and Glass (2014), women remain under-represented in top leadership positions in work organizations, a reality that reflects a variety of barriers that create a glass ceiling effect. Yet it was made mentioned in the study that age is not a factor that hampers women's stability in leadership positions. What made them not potential for the position is being assertive, which by chance, Professor Carlos clearly exemplifies, making her a qualified person to take charge of the position. Perhaps, people cannot just accept that even at her age, she can still assert things and can still debate with other people even younger than her. It is, therefore, perhaps the contributing factor to the unlikeliness of the public towards her.

Neutral polarity was demonstrated through neutral sentiments. Based on the results from the Orange text

mining, there were 13 sentiments that demonstrated neutrality as regards the appointment of Professor Carlos. Truly, this sentiment analysis allows us to identify the public attitudes towards a certain issue at hand. Most of their sentiments discussed their salute to the professor (D-54), their insight about corruption (D-38), taking a stance of Professor Carlos being the right choice (D-25), and comparing her to Meriam Defensor Santiago (D-9). According to Martin and White (2005), these sentiments were not either identified as positive or negative since, in the expressions, the lexicons may express differently from what is expected from them. These could cause confusion about the sentiments since they could not be identified whether they are positive or negative, leaving the researcher in pretty difficult sentiment analysis. And yet, since we are able to understand the contextual clues in the sentiments, then it will not be difficult to understand that some words are sometimes associated with positive, negative, or even neutral. Thus, expressions under neutral polarity are perhaps due to misidentification of the word from its collocates. The error now is on the lexicon-based method, which perhaps the definition from the dictionary is not suitable to the sentiment of the public he/she was trying to express.

Conclusion

The theoretical contributions of this research to sentiment analysis also carry practical implications for individuals interested in pedagogy, especially those focusing on research papers that incorporate sentiment analysis as a key methodological approach.

The instructor also has the opportunity to shape and refine their pedagogical approach using the insights gained from understanding how ideas are effectively communicated in meaningful discourse. The identified themes from this study hold valuable pedagogical implications. These findings can serve as a valuable resource for educators, enabling them to inform students about essential concepts related to women in leadership roles and how the public perceives and accepts female representation in high-ranking government positions or traditionally male-dominated professions. It allows for a more informed and nuanced discussion on gender dynamics and leadership, enriching the educational experience by providing real-world examples and insights drawn from sentiment analysis.

This research unveiled frequently used words through a Word Cloud, generated themes using a heatmap, and

conducted sentiment analysis of the public's opinions regarding the appointment of Prof. Clarita Carlos using Orange text mining software. For future researchers, it is recommended to explore additional analytical tools such as box plots and topic modeling to enhance sentiment analysis. Additionally, this methodology can be applied to other corpora and current issues faced by the Philippines. Given the limitation of this study, which included only 100 comments, researchers are encouraged to expand their dataset and consider incorporating data from other social networking platforms like Twitter or Instagram.

Researchers are encouraged to broaden their scope by considering data from other news agencies, as this study was limited to GMA News. This expansion would provide a more comprehensive understanding of public sentiment across various media sources and potentially yield more diverse insights.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Gideon S. Sumayo, PhD

University of Southern Mindanao – Philippines

Danilo G. Baradillo, PhD

University of the Immaculate Conception – Philippines